

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HASSAN****FIRST NAME: FUNMILAYO****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 7

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D RP6

1. Which one of these is not a basic step in academic essay writing?

- Interview participants¹**
- Researching the topic
- Organizing your ideas
- Referencing the essay

2. Which of these is a primary reason for citing sources?

- Not citing sources is wrong and unethical²**
- Citing sources gives extra marks

1. Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 17.

2. Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

- Citing sources has financial benefits
 - Citing sources makes your work more interesting
3. Which of these is not a means of presenting complex data?
- Power point.**³
 - Line graph
 - Bar Chart
 - Pie Chart
4. Sources of data are categorized into the following, except?
- Complex sources**⁴
 - Primary sources
 - Secondary sources
 - Tertiary sources
5. Testing for data reliability involves all but one of the following?
- Looking at the graphic layout of the website**⁵
 - Checking if the book or article is peer-reviewed
 - Ensuring the publisher is a reputable one
 - Checking if the writer is reputable and objective

3. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 86.

4. Turabian, 35.

5. Turabian, 42-42.

6. Which of these is a type of bibliography?

- Annotated Bibliography⁶**
- Simple Bibliography
- Complex Bibliography
- Compound Bibliography

7. Which of these is a Chapter in a Dissertation?

- Literature Review⁷**
- Objectives of the study
- The mission of the study
- Sources of data

8. The *Abstract* in a Dissertation provides:

- A concise summary description of the study⁸**
- The analysis of data
- Information regarding data sources
- Limitations and delimitations of the study

6. Turabian, 155.

7. Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 73.

8. Bloomberg and Volpe, 68.

9. The Institutional Review Board gives approval to studies involving?

- Human subjects⁹**
- Architectural designs
- The environment
- The energy sector

10. All but one of the following are qualitative research methodologies.

- Interviews¹⁰**
- Case studies
- Ethnography
- Grounded theory

9. Bloomberg and Volpe, 226.

10. Bloomberg and Volpe, 159-183.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.